

1 **ABC family transporters activated during resistance to chemotherapy in triple negative breast**
2 **cancer.**

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7 ABC family transporters identified through RNA-sequencing of two TNBC cellular systems as activated
8 during resistance to chemotherapy pertinent to MDR (multi-drug resistance) biology included *ABCG1* and
9 *ABCC1*.

10 Citations

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